

reactive species. Both the ionic strength effect and the medium polarity effect are in favour of such a neutral oxidant species.

The observation that the enolisation rates (as measured by bromination rates) are always smaller than those of oxidation, excludes the involvement of an enol intermediate in the mechanism of oxidation. Besides, a (Michaelis – Menten) plot of $1/[S]$ vs $1/k_1$ passes through the origin, which indicates the formation of a loose complex between piperidone and Ce^{IV} . A similar observation was made previously in the case of oxidation of cyclohexanone with Ce^{IV} .⁵ Finally, the introduction of acrylamide into the reaction mixture results in its polymerisation. All these observations have prompted us to propose a free radical mechanism for the oxidation (Scheme 1). The rate law for the mechanism follows equation (2).

Scheme 1

$$\frac{-d[Ce^{IV}]}{dt} = k_s K [\text{piperidone}] [Ce^{IV}] \quad (2)$$

Structure and reactivity: Although in the case of piperidones 2–4 a choice exists as to the nature of the α -hydroxyketone product (1 and 5 are symmetrical and 6 can form only one type of α -hydroxyketone), the fact that the final product contains the hydroxy group on the alkyl substituted carbon atom (as evidenced by product analysis) suggests the preferential abstraction of H-atom from the alkyl bearing α -carbon atom. The reactivity of piperidones stand in the order, $3 > 4 > 2 \sim 1 > 6 > 5$. We can group the piperidones into two categories–5 and 6, with low reactivity, constitute one group and the rest the other. The low reactivity of 5 and 6 may be attributed to steric hindrance from the alkyl substituents for the formation of the complex between piperidone and Ce^{IV} species (small K).

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Effect of Radiation on Phenobarbitone Sodium and Tetraphenobarbitone Cupratosodium in Methanolic Medium

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THE study of the effect of uv radiation on barbituric derivatives in aqueous medium has recently been done. Some of the products of degradation have been identified by comparison with hydrolysis processes, and the influence of various parameters in the reactions^{1,12,18,19} has been investigated. If the uv radiation falls in a methanolic solution containing Cu^{II} ion, redox dynamic reversible processes yield in solution the $Cu^{II} - Cu^I$ and the $CH_2OH - CH_2O$ ^{3,4,6,11,15,16,17,19}.

In view of the interest of the photochemical processes in medicinal substances and its contribution to the knowledge of allergens, we have studied the incidence of uv light on the complexes synthesised^{8,9} with barbituric ligands sensitive to uv light. The present research consists of the study of the photochemical degradation of the ligand (phenobarbital sodium) in a methanolic medium and the complex Na_2CuL_4 , to observe the processes that are taking place and also the formation of new compounds of Cu^I produced in the redox reactions with the intermediate degraded products of the ligand.

Results and Discussion

The degradation of the ligand NaL with time have been studied by following the change in absorption by the irradiated substance from zero hour to twelve hours (hour by hour) at that wavelength in which the substance has an absorption maximum (240 nm). The results are represented in Fig. 1 and it is observed that after 12 h of irradiation the species L⁻ disappeared.

Fig. 1. Variation of absorption at 240 nm of a methanolic solution of 10⁻³ M NaL solution irradiated with uv.

In second place, we tried to identify the intermediate products of the degradation of luminal, susceptible of interaction with Cu. A thin layer chromatography was carried out of the samples obtained at different times of irradiation. The results reveal that after 12 h, there exists 5 spots with different R_f values which are different from those of the species L⁻, initial which confirms the complete degradation with uv irradiation.

Lately, the solution, which had been irradiated hours at least, was separated in fractions through column chromatography obtaining the rates which are indicated in Table 1. Elemental analysis and

TABLE 1—YIELD (%) OF FRACTIONS OF IRRADIATION OF NaL

Fractions	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅
Yields (%)	1	55	21	1	20

ir and Raman spectra of the three major fractions have been also carried out. The above mentioned data along with that reported^{1,2,5} allowed us to

propose Scheme 1 of degradation, for example, fraction 5.

Scheme 1

In other research, in the irradiation of the complex Na₂CuL₄, the influence of the irradiation time was also measured; first, through a decrease in the maximum of absorbance at 510 nm, which is a characteristic⁶ of the Na₂CuL₄, and second, through the concentration measurement of the Cu^I formed in the redox processes. Figs. 2 and 3 show the results. In Fig. 2, we observe that there exists

Fig. 2. Variation of absorption at 510 nm of a methanolic solution of 2 × 10⁻⁴ M Na₂CuL₄ solution irradiated with uv.

a total photochemical degradation of the complex after approximately 3 h of radiation. In Fig. 3, we observe the existence of a redox process Cu^{II} → Cu^I; the graphs (a) and (b) show the concentration of Cu^I existing in the sample depending on the time it is left. The curve (a) corresponds to the uv irradiation while curve (b) corresponds to the uv irradiation of the sample only during the first hour.

Fig. 3. Variation of Cu^I concentration with time of $10^{-4} M \text{Na}_2\text{CuL}$ solution irradiated during (a) 95 h and (b) 1 h.

Fig. 4. Visible spectrum of Cu^I methanolic solution mixed with the fractions: (---) F_3 , (—) F_2 and (—) F_1 .

In both the cases, we observe a maximum value of the concentration of Cu^I of 32% of the total Cu^I reached in the first hour; from this very moment, both the curves develop in a different way. In curve (a), a reduction half an hour, keeps nearly constant from that moment, and in curve (b), the reduction progresses until the concentration of Cu^I

reaches zero. The behaviour of both curves are different because once it has reached the maximum value in the Cu^I concentration, an oxidation $\text{Cu}^I \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{II}$ process is produced in the case of the substance which is constantly irradiated (curve a). After 1.5 h the fraction 5 appears, which would stabilise the Cu^I avoiding the oxidation reaction,

Scheme 2

while in the substance irradiated only during the first hour (curve b), the fraction 5 has not been produced during 1 h irradiation, the oxidation reaction is complete and absorbance goes to zero.

Finally, in view to confirm that the fraction 5 is only capable to stabilise the Cu^{I} , we have mixed the fractions 2, 3 and 5 with Cu^{I} in an oxidation medium, maintaining the mixtures during 1 h. Afterwards, we ran uv-vis spectrum of each one (Fig. 4). In graphs (a) and (b), corresponding to the mixtures of fraction 2 and 3 with Cu^{I} , we observe a maximum of absorbance at 820 nm, which is a characteristic of the species Cu^{I} . While graph (c) corresponds to the mixture of fraction 5 with Cu^{I} , the maximum does not appear, and that means that the process of oxidation $\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} \rightarrow \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ did not take place in this case and hence, only fraction 5 is capable to stabilise the Cu^{I} supporting our previous conclusions¹⁴. Thus, the general process of degradation of complex Na_2CuL_4 by uv irradiation is represented in Scheme 2.

Experimental

The ir spectra (CsI) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi 577 spectrophotometer, uv-vis spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi 200 spectrophotometer, and Raman spectra on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi R-24 spectrometer using solvent RM 50.

The irradiation was done in a photochemical immersion reactor with a H2L mercury lamp of a medium pressure containing the metabolic solution of NaL ($3.10^{-2} M$) and keeping the relations $\text{NaL}/\text{Cu}^{\text{I}} = 70(9)$ for obtaining the complex.

Chromatographic papers Pl 60 F (0.200 nm) were used for the tlc. The papers were soaked with solutions of I2 and irradiated with uv light, the eluent being $\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$ and CH_3OH . To separate the fractions by chromatography a column of silica gel (Merck 60 0.63-0.200 nm) using eluents from a lower to a higher polarity for each fraction (Cl_4CH ; Cl_3C ; $\text{CH}_3-\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5-\text{CH}_3\text{OH}$ 50% and CH_3OH) was used. Five fractions were isolated (Table 1). Fractions 1, 2, 3 and 4, were found to be mixtures of more than one component, whose structures could not be determined. However, fraction 5 (the only one which interacts with Cu^{I}) was tentatively identified as *N*-(2-phenylbutanoyl)-*N'*-(methoxycarbonylurea),

ν_{max} 3 500-3 000 br (NH) and 1 590 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}=\text{O}$); δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.6 (5H, m, C_6H_5), 3.9 (3H, s, OCH_3), 2.4 (2H, m, CH_2) and 1.2 (3H, t, CH_3).

The determination of Cu^{I} was done with neocuproine^{7,20} at pH 9 and measured¹⁰. Calibration was done with the help CuCl (Merck r.a., $1.6 \times 10^{-4} - 8.0 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Phenobarbitone sodium (NaL) was obtained from Bayer S.A. Laboratories.

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